

Production of Cake Using Lemon Grass as Flavoring Agent

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Abstract:

*Lemongrass has numerous uses and important health benefits. Lemongrass had a strong flavor and was used as flavoring agent in sponge cake production. The objectives of the study were to: find out if it would be possible to process lemongrass to be used as flavoring agent in cake making, find out if the lemongrass would be accepted by consumers and conduct a sensory evaluation on lemongrass cake. The study employed an experimental research design, and a questionnaire was used to collect data from eighty (80) respondents. Data obtained was analyzed using Statal Package for Service Solution (SPSS). The study found that majority of the respondents had not eaten cakes flavored with lemongrass before. However, respondents accepted cake flavored with lemongrass. Majority of the respondents affirmed that they would patronize cake made with lemongrass. **Keywords:** Cake, Lemongrass, Sensory evaluation, Flavouring agent.*

1 Background

Lemongrass *Cymbopogon citratus* is an aromatic perennial tall grass with rhizomes and densely tufted fibrous root. It has short underground stems with ringed segments, coarse, green slightly leathery leaves in dense clusters (Nambia & Matela, 2012). Lemongrass is grown throughout Africa, in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), Angola, Madagascar and Comoros lands. In the western world, it is often used in curries, marinades and seafood soups, added to salads in Vietnam. It is used for the preparation of soft drinks and as an aromatic, pleasant-tasting herbal tea all around its distribution area in Peru. In addition to its culinary usage, lemongrass offers a wide array of medicinal benefits and is in extensive demand due to its antibacterial, anti-fungal and antimicrobial properties across Southeast Asia, as well as the African and American continents (Orrego, Leiva & Cheel 2009). Stehmann (1995) reported that lemongrass tea also has diuretic properties and can help in urinating difficulties and water retention.

The cake is a form of sweet dessert that is typically baked. In its oldest forms, cakes were modifications of bread but now cover a wide range of preparations that can be simple or elaborate and share features with other desserts such as pastries, meringues, custards, and pies (Ayto, 2002). Cake ingredients are flour, sugar, eggs, butter or oil, liquid, and leavening agents, such as baking soda and/or baking powder. Common additional ingredients and flavorings include dried, candied or fresh fruit, nuts, cocoa, and extracts such as vanilla, with numerous substitutions for the primary ingredients (Castella, 2010).

1.1 Research Problem

Lemongrass is widely used as a culinary herb in Asian cuisines and also as a medicinal herb in India. It has a subtle citrus flavor and can be dried and powdered, or used fresh. It is commonly used in teas, soups, and curries. It is also suitable for use with poultry, fish, beef, and seafood. It is often used as a tea in African countries such as Togo and the Democratic Republic of the Congo and Latin American countries such as Mexico (Bleasel, Tate & Rademaker, 2002). The health benefits of lemongrass include relief from stomach disorders, insomnia, respiratory disorders, fever, aches, infections, rheumatism, and edema. It is also effective in treating type 2 diabetes, cancer, and obesity, in addition aiding in detoxification. Aside the diverse use of lemon grass; it is used in the manufacturing of various products such as fragrances because of its extended shelf life, owing to the low amount of myrcene in that variety. Despite the numerous uses and important of lemon grass, it has not been used in cake making. It is in this regard that the researchers produce cake using lemon grass as flavouring agent to create a variation in the market.

1.2 Purpose of the study

The study sought to process lemon grass to be used as flavouring agent in cake making. The objectives of the study were to: find out if it would be possible to process lemon grass as a flavouring agent in cake making, find out the acceptability of lemongrass cake by consumers and to conduct a sensory evaluation on lemon grass cake.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Overview of Lemon Grass

According to Negrelle and Gomes (2007), *Cymbopogon citratus* also known as Lemongrass is an herb which belongs to the grass family of Poaceae. It is well known and utilized for its distinct lemon flavor and citrusy aroma. It is a tall, perennial grass which is native to India and tropical regions of Asia. It is a coarse and tufted plant with linear leaves that grows in thick bunches, emerging from a strong base and standing for about 3 metres in height with a metre-wide stretch.

Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) is easy to grow herb that requires warm, humid conditions, full sunlight and plenty of moisture. It is a tender perennial that is commonly grown as an annual in cooler areas. Plant lemongrass after the last frost or grow it in a pot and move it outdoors after temperatures warm in the spring. Nurseries and seed companies will generally sell small starter plants (Bleasel, Tate, and Rademaker, 2002).

Blanco, Costa, Freire, Santos and Costa (2009) emphasized that the genus *Cymbopogon* comprises of 55 species of grass, two of which are referred to as Lemongrass. These are West Indian lemongrass or *Cymbopogon citratus* which is famously preferred for culinary use and East Indian lemongrass or *Cymbopogon flexuosus* which is used in the manufacturing of various products such as fragrances because of its extended shelf life, owing to the low amount of myrcene in that variety.

2.2 Nutritional and Health Benefits of Lemon Grass

The health benefits of lemongrass include relief from stomach disorders, insomnia, respiratory disorders, fever, aches, infections, rheumatism, and edema. The defensive antioxidant activity of the lemongrass herb protects against antibiotic-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and helps in maintaining optimum cholesterol levels, cellular health, nervous system, healthy skin and immune system (Bremness, 2002). It is also effective in treating type 2 diabetes, cancer, and obesity, while also aiding in detoxification. It is extensively used in aromatherapy and helps to combat fatigue, anxiety and body odour (Bremness, 2002).

Lemongrass contains several flavonoids that function as antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents. In their antioxidant capacity, flavonoids prevent damage to cells that can lead to long-term diseases such as heart disease or arthritis. One flavonoid in lemongrass called luteolin has the ability to slow the growth and hasten the death of certain types of cancer cells (European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2012). Luteolin also has such strong anti-inflammatory abilities that it may be able to treat some symptoms of multiple sclerosis, as well as lung infections or acute lung injury. Lemon grass is rich in nutrients such as carbohydrates, protein, and fat, Vitamin A, B, and C in traces. The essential oils in lemongrass add to these benefits, as they also slow the growth of cancer cells, especially in liver and breast cancers and leukemia, as stated by Busch, (2016).

2.3 Cakes and Cake Making

Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN, 2012) defined cake as a 'sweet baked' product usually containing flour, sugar, eggs and fat. Other typical ingredients are flavouring agents, liquids and leaveners or raising agents, such as baking powder or baking soda. Cakes are generally categorized by their main ingredient or flavouring. For example Cheesecake, Chocolate cake or raspberry cake, Fruit cake. Or by their method of preparation: Mousse cake, Chiffon cake, Flourless cake (Campos, Davide, Soares, Viccini, 2008).

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research design for this study was experimental. Experimental research is a controlled study in which the researcher attempts to understand cause and effect relationships. The researcher controlled the variable to get the desired results. The researcher used different ingredients and methods to produce lemon grass cake. The researcher purchased the lemongrass from lemongrass cultivator. The fresh lemon grass was sorted to separate

unwanted materials from it, washed with brine thoroughly and blended into smooth mixture then for production. A sample size for this study was eighty (80) respondents. The study employed purposive sampling to select respondents for the research. Different samples from the finished products were displayed for respondents to conduct sensory evaluate the product using a structured questionnaire. Data obtained were carefully edited and analyzed using Statistical Package for Service Solution (SPSS) Version 21.0

3.1 Product Development:

In the sample preparation, lemon grass was thoroughly washed before used. The lemon grass was blended into a smooth mixture and added to the cake mixture after adding the creamed fat to the whisked eggs as a flavoring agent.

Table 1: Cake Ingredients and Quantities

Ingredients	SAMPLE A: 100% (Lemon Grass)	SAMPLE B: 100% Strawberry	SAMPLE C: 50% Lemongrass and 50% Strawberry
Flour	400g	400g	400g
Sugar	200g	200g	200g
Baking powder	2 teaspoon	2 teaspoon	2 teaspoon
Eggs	6 pieces	6 pieces	6 pieces
Margarine	300g	300g	300g
Blended lemongrass	2 teaspoon	-	1 teaspoon
Strawberry	-	2 teaspoon	1 teaspoon

Figure 1: Ingredients for Lemongrass Cake

Margarine

Soft flour

Eggs

Lemongrass

Baking powder

Sugar

Figure 2: Flow chart for preparation of lemon grass cake

Figure 3: Processes Involved in the Production of Lemon Grass cake

Fresh Lemongrass

Chop Lemongrass

blend lemongrass

Blended Lemongrass

Ingredients mixed together to form a mixture flavouring

Figure 4: Samples

Product A: 100% Lemongrass flavoured cake

Product B: 100% Strawberry flavoured Cake

Product C: 50% Lemongrass and 50% Strawberry flavoured Cake

Product A

Product B

Product C

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Eighty (80) copies of questionnaires were administered during the analytical measurement. The analysis first presents the demographic data of respondents followed by the items in the questionnaires based on the objectives of the study.

Background Information on Respondents

This table presents the demographic distribution of respondents; it can be seen from the table that majority of the respondents (88%) were females and only 12% were males. Respondents had different ages ranging from 15-41 years. More than half of the respondents (65%) aged between 15-31 years which indicated that they are in the early adult ages and 13 % of the respondents were between 41 years and above.

Table 2: Demographic data of respondents

Characteristic	Respondents		
	N	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	80		
Male		10	12
Female		70	88
Age (years)	80		
15 – 25		27	34
26 – 31		25	31
31 – 40		18	22
41 years and above		10	13

Knowledge of Lemon grass

When respondents were asked whether they knew lemongrass, the majority of the respondents (81%) said they knew lemon grass while a few (19%) of the respondents did not know lemon grass. Lemon grass is a very common plant that grows mostly on backyards or small farms. According to Nambia, and Matela, (2012) lemon grass is an aromatic perennial tall grass with rhizomes and densely tufted fibrous root. It has short underground stems with ringed segments, coarse, green slightly leathery leaves in dense clusters.

Figure 5: Respondents’ knowledge of lemongrass.

Respondents’ Information about Lemongrass

Table 3: Response on what respondents knew about lemon grass

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
It is used for tea	61	76
It used for medicinal purpose	13	16
It has health benefits	6	8
Total	80	100

A follow up question was asked on what respondents knew about lemon grass, from the table it can be seen that majority of respondents (76%) mentioned that lemon grass is mostly used for tea, 16% indicated that lemon grass has medicinal purposes and few of the respondents (8%) said it has lot of health benefits. This result

confirms the assertion by Bleasel, Tate, and Rademaker (2002) that lemon grass is used for the preparation of soft drinks and as an aromatic, pleasant- tasting herbal tea all around its distribution area in Peru. In Java, it is used in the preparation of highly spiced “sherbet.” Lemongrass is used in preparations such as kadha, which is a traditional herbal brew used against coughs, colds, etc.

Using Lemongrass as flavouring agent

Figure 6: Response on whether lemongrass can be used as flavouring agents

Respondents were asked whether lemongrass could be used as flavouring agents in cake making, the greater percentage of the respondents (81%) affirmed that lemon grass could be used as a flavouring agent while 19% of respondents disagreed to that opinion. Puatanachokchai, Kishida, Denda, Murata, Konishi, Vinitkekumnuen and Nakae (2002) stated that lemongrass contains flavonoids and phenolic compounds such as luteolin, glycosides, quercetin, kaempferol, elimicin, catecol, chlorogenic acid, and caffeic acid, all of which help in providing an impressive range of medicinal aids. Thus, can be used as flavouring agent in some preparation.

Food products flavoured with lemongrass

Figure 7: Response to whether respondents have seen food product flavoured with lemongrass

On the notion of whether respondents have seen or come by food products flavoured with lemongrass, more than half of the respondents (69%) opposed to that assertion and few (31%) agreed. This implied that majority of respondents selected for this study in Takoradi have not come by any product flavouring agent with lemon grass. However, Bleasel, Tate, and Rademaker, (2002) who indicated that in the western world, it is often used in curries, marinades, and sea foods soups, added to salads in Vietnam. They also they added that it is used for the preparation of soft drinks and as an aromatic, pleasant- tasting herbal tea all around its distribution area in Peru. In Java, it is used in the preparation of highly spiced “sherbet.” With regards to whether respondents have

ever eaten cake before, all the respondents affirmed that they had eaten cake before. This result indicated that majority of the respondents sampled had eaten cake before.

Different cake flavours

Figure 8: Consumption of different cake flavours

In an attempt to find out the flavor of the food that was eaten by respondents, 44% of the respondents said they had eaten vanilla flavoured cake, 28% of the respondents indicated that they enjoyed strawberry flavored cake, 22% of the respondents mentioned chocolate flavor cake as their favourite, and only 6% of the respondents also mentioned that they enjoyed other flavoures such as banana, butter scotch, among others. Castella (2010) posited that the common additional ingredients and flavorings added to cakes include dried, candied or fresh fruit, nuts, cocoa, and extracts such as vanilla, with numerous substitutions for the primary ingredients.

4.7 Cake flavoured with lemongrass

Figure 9: Consumption of Lemongrass cake

When respondents were asked whether they have eaten cakes flavoured with lemongrass, Majority of the respondents (94%) said they have never eaten cakes flavoured with lemongrass, while only 6% of the respondents said they had eaten cakes flavoured with lemongrass. This showed lemongrass had not been used as flavouring agents in cake making. This result is obvious as this study sort to prepare a cake with lemongrass thereby making it known to the public. According to Negrelle and Gomes (2007), *Cymbopogon citratus* also known as Lemongrass is an herb which belongs to the grass family of Poaceae. It is well known and utilized for its distinct lemon flavor and citrusy aroma.

Sensory Evaluation of products

This section analyzed respondents' view on the various samples produced.

Samples

Product A: 100% Lemongrass flavoured cake

Product B: 100% Strawberry flavoured Cake

Product C: 50% Lemongrass and 50% Strawberry flavoured Cake

Cake made with only Lemongrass flavor (Product A)

Table 4: Sensory Evaluation for Product A

Sensory	Very good		Good		Average		Poor		Very poor	
	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%
Colour	70	88	6	8	4	5	0	0	0	0
Taste	72	90	6	8	2	3	0	0	0	0
Aroma	60	52	5	6	10	13	2	3	3	4
Texture	40	50	25	31	10	13	5	6	0	0

Table 5 presents respondents' views on Product A; the actual products made up a cake made with lemongrass as the flavouring agent. Concerning the colour, the majority of the respondents (88%) said the colour of the product was very good, only 5% of the respondents indicated that the colour of the product was average. Concerning the Taste, almost all the respondents (90%) indicated Product A; almost all the respondents said cake made with lemongrass tasted very well. Also, the products had a perfect aroma, as 52% of the respondents affirmed, and 19% said the aroma was average and only 3% said the aroma was poor. Finally, half of the respondents (50%) indicated the texture Product A was very good 31% said it was good, and 5% indicated that the texture of Product A was poor. Similarly, Lonkar, Chavan, Pawar, Bansode, and Amarowicz, (2013) study on the sensory evaluation of fresh and stored lemongrass powder. The results indicated that the mean score for the colour of powder was 7.84, the colour extract was 7.85, aroma of extract 7.69, the taste of extract 7.94 and overall acceptability was 7.83. The colour of powder, the colour of extract, aroma of extract, the taste of extract and overall acceptability is better in 'Krishna' variety powder which was 8.22 followed by CKP-25 powder and 'Kaveri' powder.

Product B: Cake made with strawberry

Table 5: Sensory Evaluation for Product B

Sensory	Very good		Good		Average		Poor		Very poor	
	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%	Frq	%
Colour	50	63	20	25	10	13	0	0	0	0
Taste	40	50	15	19	15	19	0	0	0	0
Aroma	40	50	15	19	20	25	5	6	0	0
Texture	60	75	10	13	10	13	0	0	0	0

Table 5 presents a sensory analysis for Product B which is a cake made with strawberry flavor. It can be seen that with regards to colour, the majority of the respondents (63%) affirmed the colour was very good. Again, 38% of the respondents were of the view that the colour was a good to average. Concerning the taste of Product

B, it has been indicated that the products had a perfect taste (50%).Also, 50% affirmed very well and good respectively. The aroma of Product B was very good (50%), and only 6% of the respondents said the aroma was poor. On the notion of the texture of Product B, the majority of the respondents indicated it was good, only 13% said the texture was average. According to Davidek, Illmann, Gou´ezec, Rytz, Schuchmann and Blank (2009) to cake and cookie recipes include a variety of flavorings. Some common flavorings are salt, vanilla, chocolate, spices, lemon extract, almond extract, butter flavoring, and many others. Although these flavorings are used only in small amounts, they have a big impact on flavor.

Cake made with both Lemongrass and Strawberry Flavour

Table 6: Sensory Evaluation for Product C

Sensory	Very good		Good		Average		Poor		Very poor	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Colour	50	63	15	19	10	13	0	0	0	0
Taste	45	40	15	19	15	19	0	0	0	0
Aroma	50	63	20	25	0	0	10	13	0	0
Texture	50	63	20	25	10	13	0	0	0	0

Product C sensory as indicated in the table shows that majority of the respondents (82%) liked the colour, as 59% also indicated that the taste was perfect with exception 19% who mentioned that the taste was avergely good. More than half of the respondents found the respondents (77%) said the product c had a fantastic aroma whiles 13% of the respondent disagreed with that opinion as the indicated the aroma was poor. Finally, the texture Product C was incredible, as 63% indicated very good, 25% chose good and average by another 13% of the total respondents.

Figure 6: Response to the product that was enjoyed most by respondents

With regards to the product that was enjoyed most by respondents, it can be seen from the figure 4.6 that, the majority of the respondents (81%) enjoyed Product A (which is a cake made with lemongrass as flavor only). Few of the respondents, 10% and 9% enjoyed Product B and C respectively as shown in figure 4.6. This result showed that majority of the respondents enjoyed a cake made with lemon grass more than cakes made with other flavouring agents.

Figure 9: Respondents willingness to patronize lemongrass cake

Respondents were asked whether they will patronize cakes made with lemon grass, almost all the respondents (94%) affirmed that they would like a patronize cake made with lemongrass flavouring. This implied that majority of the respondents (94%) who participated in the study have accepted cake made with lemongrass flavouring agents.

Table 7: Reason for patronizing lemon grass cake

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
It tasty and attractive	40	50
To have variety	25	31
It is nutritious	15	19
Total	80	100

With regards to the reasons why respondents would patronize lemon grass cake, half of the respondents (50%) indicated that lemongrass cakes were tasty and delicious. Also, 31% of the respondents said cake made with lemon flavor add variety to the normal cakes on the market while only 19% of the respondents indicated that cake made with lemon flavor are nutritious. Orrego, Leivaand, and Cheel (2009) stated that in addition to its culinary usage, lemongrass offers a wide array of medicinal benefits and is in extensive demand due to its antibacterial, anti-fungal and antimicrobial properties across Southeast Asia, as well as the African and American continents.

Table 8: Respondents' recommendations for Lemongrass Cake

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Produce in large quantity	50	64
Promoted on the market	20	25
Caterers should be encouraged to use lemongrass	10	13
Total	80	100

With regards to the recommendations given by respondents, 64% of the respondents said the cake should be produced in large quantity for sale, 25% stated that it should be promoted in large quantity and 13% of the respondents said caterers should be encouraged to use lemongrass as flavouring agents in cake making.

Conclusions

The study concluded the taste, aroma, flavour, colour, and texture of the lemon grass were acceptable and preferred to the other flavoured cake. Respondents said lemongrass cake was tasty and nutritious and had a perfect texture.

Based on the findings, the recommendations are: lemongrass should be promoted, and caterers should be encouraged to adopt the use of lemongrass in their preparation of dishes especially in cake making as a flavouring agent. Nutritionist and dietitian should educate the public and encourage them to use lemongrass in producing products and even in food preparation.

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